

Complementary Roles of Parents in Educating Exceptional Children: Keys to Boosting Literacy

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Abstract

Education is the most effective means of achieving literacy and human development. The child is at the center of most educational programmes. The essence is to make him become literate and knowledgeable about himself and his environment thereby contributing to development of the society. Every child therefore has a right to quality education, but some groups of children are at disadvantaged position to access quality education. They find it difficult to benefit adequately from normal school activities in regular school setting. Worse still, they are most often not monitored by their parents. These children are termed exceptional children or children with special needs. Every exceptional child has special needs as a result of deviation in his/her make-up. This paper, examined the complementary roles parents can play at home in the education of their exceptional children. This is based on the fact that there are some roles considered germane to boost literacy of this special population. These roles amongst others include: acting as teachers, partners with other professionals in decision making, advocacy on behalf of the child to other stake holders and follow up of the child's school work at home. The parents should equally act as supervisors and first contact for early interventions. The paper therefore examined the concept of exceptionality. Educational programme cum boosting of sustainable literacy for exceptional children, and complementary roles of parents to boosting literacy for the exceptional children. It was recommended among others that parents should be made aware of these pertinent roles they should play to boost literacy of their exceptional child.

Key words: Complementary role, parents, education, exceptional child, boosting literacy

Introduction

Formal education has become a very popular form of education basically due to its emphasis on literacy. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) asserted that education is compulsory and a right

of every Nigerian irrespective of gender, social status, religion, ethnic background and any peculiar individual challenges. Encarta (2009) perceives literacy as the ability to read and write to a competent level. Literacy which is ability to read and

write in its simplest definition is therefore the right of every child and the aim of education of the child is to make him/her literate. This no doubt makes him develop skills necessary to function effectively in the society, live independent and fulfilled live. The above assertion is supported by Silue, (2000) in Erickson (2005) who posited a strong positive correlation between development and literacy because literacy impacts virtually every domain of live. To achieve this, a lot of educational programmes have been put in place severally for many years, to make each child receive a certain minimum education.

According to Erickson (2005), there is an increasing body of evidence from developed and developing countries to guide efforts to ensure that all children, including those with disabilities learn to read and write. The instructional strategies and condition for which children will benefit maximally and yield result from all educational activities are the matters at stake. The education of the child traditionally lies in the hands of the teachers who are professionally trained and equipped to handle it. The classroom teacher is saddled with the responsibility of meeting the academic, social and psychological needs of the child. He/she is faced with caring for many children entrusted into his/her care. It becomes sometimes very difficult to give adequate attention to all the children.

The issue of concern in this paper is that there are some groups of children who do not benefit from the regular classroom setting and need to be given special support for learning to take place. These are the exceptional children or children with special needs and these needs among others, include special education. Some of them experience intellectual impairments that influence their ability to

learn, interact or communicate with others. According to Ikpaya (2001), in various cultures, most of these children are exempted from regular classroom programme. According to the author, in Nigerian culture, there are no unbiased standardized test instruments for use in formal identification of these children with special need. The regular classroom settings are usually mainstreamed. Most of the problems are only identified at school age especially in African setting due to lack of knowledge and financial limitations of the parents. Furthermore, the individual functioning of these children are influenced by the lack of supports and opportunities provided by their socio-cultural surroundings. Consequent to this is late interventions. Some of the children are neglected and finally abandoned at home. They become insignificant and invariably liabilities to both family and the society.

Special education programme is the instrument that is specially designed to meet the unique needs of these children who are exceptional and it requires team effort (Hussey, 2016). No wonder the FRN (2013) perceived special education as customized education programme for those that cannot benefit from general education. The classroom or regular teachers, who have no formal training on how to handle this special population, most often play important role in assessing, supporting and teaching them but lack of professional skills by these teachers affects the quality of their service delivery to these children thereby limiting the expected result in the area of improvement in their skills of reading and writing. The little or much of learning experiences these children get from such school setting is not reinforced by their parents. This presumed negligence of duty by parents might be due to

ignorance of their germane complementary roles. Nevertheless, according to the National Council of Special Education (NCSE), (2014), the family is the primary and natural educator of the Child. The council posits that parents see their child's development at first hand and are most likely to notice if learning is or not progressing well especially in the case of literate parents. This invariably means that both parents and teachers have important roles to play in the education of the exceptional children. Sahagun (2015) proposes that their roles do not replace but rather complement and reinforce each other's, thus providing the children with a consistent message about reading and learning. She also posits that having a good working relationship between teachers and parents is an important part of a student's success. Quebec's Education Act 1997 sees parents as partners in school management (Deslandes, 2001). Parental involvement in the education of their exceptional child in partnership with the teacher is a mutual sharing of task or responsibilities hence it is described as a reciprocal partnership by Bouchard (1998) in Deslandes, (2001). In the same vein, Christenson and Sheridan (2001) in Sahagun (2015) explained that "thinking of parents and teachers as "partners" refers to this mutual effort towards a shared goal. It also implies shared responsibilities of parents and teachers for supporting students as learners. In the light of the above assertions, this paper therefore x-rayed the concept of exceptionality and the different education programmes for the exceptional children. It highlighted the different complementary roles of parents and strategies of using the roles to boost literacy of exceptional children. This

parents to boost literacy of this special population.

Concept of Exceptionality

Every child has educational need but a child with special educational need falls under the group that is called exceptional children. Eke (2000) conceived exceptionality as deviation from physical, social, mental, psychological among others in an individual's make up. There are two main groups of exceptionality viz- positive (the gifted and talented) and the negative (the disabled). These are children who cannot maximize learning in a regular classroom setting due to certain limiting factors which may be inherent within them caused by physical or physiological challenges. According to Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) updated information (2012), definitions of exceptional children vary widely across countries as they are specific to each country's legislation. However, general opinion agrees that a child is commonly recognized as having special educational need, that is, (exceptional child) if he or she is not able to benefit from the school education made generally available for children of the same age without additional support or adaptations in the content of studies (OECD 2012).

In the same vein, Ikpaya (2001) sees exceptional children as children who cannot maximize learning with regular class instruction because of their remarkably varied abilities, academically or otherwise, and require special education in order to achieve their maximum potential. Heward (2014) describes them as children who are not in the normal curve when it comes to academics, social development and/or learning abilities. According to the author, they differ from the norm (either below

or above) to the extent that they require special education and related services to fully benefit from education. In other words, these are children who experience, according to Heward, difficulty in learning that makes them perform below the normal curve and also those whose performance is so superior that they perform at an accelerated rate and as such there is need for modification in curriculum and instruction to help them fulfill their potentials.

In summary, exceptional children therefore include children with learning and/or behaviour problems, physical disabilities or sensory impairment and children who are intellectually gifted or specially talented (Heward, 2014). Education for persons with special needs Acts 2004 sums the following four areas of disabilities. These are: physical, sensory, mental health and learning disabilities. Heward (2014) opines that some exceptional children share the following characteristics: mental retardation also called intellectual disability, learning disabilities, emotional and behavioral disorders, autism, communication (speech and language disorders), hearing impairments, visual impairments, physical and health impairments, traumatic brain injury, multiple disabilities, giftedness and special talents. The general learning disability can be at the level of mild, moderate, severe or profound and all of them are referred to as "at risk population".

Educational programme and boosting sustainable literacy for Exceptional Children

It is imperative to note that educational programme for this special population in their formative ages especially primary through basic education level

is intertwined with their literacy level. They are not separated but rather used interchangeably especially in this work hence literacy is all about reading and writing which is derived from formal education where education programmes stem from. It is an established fact that all children including children with special educational needs, have right to quality education. The above assertion of education being the right of every child which no doubt includes the exceptional children has been reiterated by FRN in 2013. The FRN in the National Policy on Education enumerated five aims and objectives of Special Needs Education and listed several strategies to actualize them. These aims and objectives could end up being mere wishes if nothing is done to involve the parents in the actualization. Educational programme for exceptional children are basically planned according to their needs and class or category of exceptionality. The programme for these children is provided through a variety of arrangements and alternatives. The learning experiences are organized at their own pace, for maximum self-development.

According to the National Council for Special Education (NCSE (2014), the aims of education for all children are the same and education is meant to support children to develop in all aspects of their lives - spiritual, moral, cognitive, emotional, imaginative, aesthetic, social and physical. FRN (2004) states that education is meant to enable all the children to develop according to their ability, live fulfilled lives and contribute their quota to the development of the nation. The main concern of all stakeholders is that children with special educational needs be educated where ever possible.

Education programme for exceptional children starts with early diagnosis, assessment and then intervention by stakeholders which include professionals from different sectors. In technologically advanced countries, a team of service providers includes: administrator, regular class teacher, special education teacher, school counselor, school nurse, psychometrics, other health personnels, parents and community members (Ikpaya, 2001). In the case of Nigeria, the team members as provided by the FRN in Ikpaya (2001) guideline include the following: administrators (principal/headmaster), regular class teachers, special education teachers and different communities, councils and ministries that provide coordination and supporting services. In Nigerian situation, there is no official provision for the position of parents as members of the team service providers and that is the position this paper sought to take because no educational programme organized for exceptional children will be successful or meaningful without official participation of parents hence this paper posits that complementary roles of parents will be necessary for effective implementation of any educational programme for exceptional children. The essence of boosting literacy for this special population through a well organized educational programme is not targeted to be short lived. It has to be planned to last long so as to enhance sustainability.

Educational Programme for Exceptional Children

The major desire of stakeholders in the educational programme of exceptional children is that these children with special educational needs be educated, wherever possible, in an inclusive environment with children who do not have such

challenges. The exception to this role is where assessment proves that inclusion will not be to the best interest of the child with special needs or when it will not also be to the interest of the other children in the class. In inclusive setting the system is adjusted to meet the children's need. The children with special educational needs could be placed in mainstream class; special class or special school.

In the mainstream class, the regular teacher has primary responsibility to take care of all the children without special needs in the class together with the children with special needs. This regular teacher could be given teaching support or resource teacher such as a special education teacher to help him or her when necessary. Special class could also be created for children with special needs in a mainstream school. These children are taken care of by special education teachers. Special schools could also be created according to the categories of disability e.g. hearing impairment (deaf) or school for the gifted. Depending on the severity of the disability, a child could be placed on home-school plan where visiting teachers provide specialist services and guidance to parents and the children. Visiting teachers, could also visit schools to provide guidance, support and specialist teaching to pupils and teachers on the use of assistive technology. A certain number of children who have more complex needs can be given individualized education programmes in school or at home and additional learning support hours may be given to teachers to enable them handle these children with complex needs. Programme placements are made based on each student's education programme and need which includes academic, linguistic, social-emotional, motor and health needs.

Complementary roles of parents to boost the literacy of the exceptional child

The position of the parents as link between the home and other major stakeholders in the education of their children is very important. Most importantly the parental involvement in the classroom, home learning, and in decision making are essential in the education programme of their exceptional children. The children that are non-exceptional may not pose any challenge to parents as those children that are exceptional. The exceptional child is operationally perceived here as those in preprimary, primary and basic education that are either gifted/talented or disabled whose handicap manifest in areas of reading and writing. The gifted child might have all it takes to do well but may not outlive that due to actions and inactions of the teachers and parents. The disabled themselves are with impairment and obvious handicaps inhibiting literacy skills. Some of these handicaps that abound among this special population can be significantly minimized by the complementary roles of the parents. These children could be at their formative ages and as such under the close watch and supervision of their parents.

It is worthy to note that the exceptional children have interest, passion, potentialities, aptitudes and abilities. The roles of the parents are the leeway to uncover and utilize such latent traits in them. After all, it is said there is ability in disability and that the geniuses or the gifted rule the world. That justified the clarion call for the complementary role of parents. Whatever goes on in the school regarding writing and reading skills could be complemented by the parents through follow up at home. Schools and teachers alone seldom help students achieve their full academic potential. This

is not an indictment of schools and teachers. Rather, it is a fact that child development, students' personal investment in academics and interest for learning, for example, are influenced by parental messages (Bempechat, 198 & Coleman 1987 in Todd, Beamer & Goodreau, 2014), therefore, the approach for interacting with families should be characterized by focusing on the importance of the relationship and establishing meaningful co-roles for the partners. Working as partners is a way of thinking about how to create constructive connections between parents and teachers. Forming connections means developing an intentional and ongoing relationship between teachers and parents that is designed to enhance children's learning, and to address the obstacles that impede it. It requires delivery of the right message: that mutual respect and independence of home, school and the community are essential to children's development (McAfee, 1993 in Todd, Beamer & Goodreau, 2014)

Teachers are professionals that have been prepared by virtue of their training, to be classroom managers, deliver instruction and coordinate a variety of specialists activities pertaining to teaching and learning. They occupy a very important position in every educational programme but they alone, cannot meet the challenges of children with special educational need, hence the complementary roles of parents in the education of these children are very inevitable. According to Todd, Beamer and Goodreau (2014). Teachers, especially special education teachers face time constraints, curriculum demands, limited resources and large classes. All these affect the quality of attention they can give to the children. According to the authors, the teachers' constraints interfere with their

empathy of the challenges parents face at home in caring for the children while parents sometimes on their own part, make unrealistic demands on teachers. Todd, Beamer and Goodreau (2014) therefore posited that the solution to the different viewpoints is that both teachers and parents should complement each other in their roles; none of the parties should undermine the role of the other but rather complement and reinforce each other's effort. Parents need to complement the work of teachers and both parents and teachers or schools need to partner together in making informed decisions concerning the education of their children (National Council for Special Education (NCSE) 2014).

"The family is the primary and natural educator of the child according to the article 42 of the Irish constitution" (NCSE 2014, p14). The parents have first-hand information about their child's development and as such must be actively involved in any and many discussions and decisions pertaining to education of their child. They can play key role in providing information about the child's abilities, interest, strength and weakness. The parents can therefore complement the role of the teachers and the other stakeholders in the educational programme of their exceptional children in the following ways: -

Shearer and Shearer (1977) in Mahoney, Kaiser, Girolametto, MacDonald, Robinson, Safford, and Spiker (1999), posited that parents may act as teachers, partners, decision makers and/or advocates. To them, they are teachers when they reinforce the skills acquired in pre-school; they are partners when they communicate needs with school personnel and decision makers when they participate in intervention education programme process. They are in the

position to give relevant information within their knowledge about their child's needs to the teacher and the school to aid them in their decision making about the child in terms of his placement and transition to any other programme, class or school. Parents should follow up on their child's progress report so as to know when changes are needed in order to meet their changing needs and abilities. They should follow up homework at home and should know what to do and stand in the gap in the absence of the professionals or teachers that handle the child. Parents should present the child for early intervention programme and seek early intervention facilities. If the child is placed on home schooling plan, the parents can employ the services of visiting teachers and act as middle persons between the home- school providers and the child.

Parental involvement in home learning will include school work, encouragement and compliments to the child to boost his interest. Parents can help to supervise the child at home, provide guidance and the needed materials for the child. They can give feedback about how the child is progressing and cooperating with instruction at home to the teachers and other service providers. Parents should partner with school management in decision making. They should get proper diagnostic report of the child's problems from professionals, visit the school where their child is to attend and evaluate the facilities, gather information about the educational programme and options that may be available for the child and seek professional advice from the professionals before taking final decision on the child's education programme for maximum benefits.

The complementary roles of parents can only help to boost literacy if the

parents actually know about the whole business of helping their exceptional child become educated. Most parents do not know where to begin to help their kids. This can be basically attributed to many factors. First and foremost, the parents may be unable to read and write, secondly, they may not know where to get help or direction, and they may be ignorant of the services that are available for their children. Again, they may have high expectations from the teacher, thinking that the responsibility of educating the child should be borne by the teacher alone. Epstein (1992) asserts that parents who are less involved in the schooling of their children are usually non-traditional families with lower levels of education. The parents' understanding of their role determines the type of activities they will consider necessary when interacting with their children. It also influences their views on child development, child-rearing and home support roles.

In the light of the above assertions, there is need for the parents to be enhanced by the government to be involved formally into the planning of the educational programme of their exceptional children as part of the team of service providers. Epstein's (2001) model assumes that an exchange of skills, abilities and interests between parents and teachers that are based upon mutual respect and a sharing of common goals will benefit children's learning and development. Parents should be made to understand their obligations towards their children. They should be made to be aware of their expectations and be given training on how to help their children learn at home. They should be made to be aware of the options available to their children in terms of intervention programmes, placement and enrollment in a special

teachers' services or home class.

Conclusion

This paper reviewed literature on the concept of exceptionality and educational programme for children with special needs. It traversed the roles the parents, regular teachers, special teachers and other professionals in the allied areas are to play in order to boost literacy of this special population. Therefore, the position of this paper is that if parents are made aware of their roles that complement that of the professionals, the desire to boost literacy for the exceptional children should be achieved. Beyond that, the sustainability of literacy shall be guaranteed. This is on the premise that no one group can do it alone hence the advocacy of this paper on the complementary roles of parents of exceptional children.

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